

INFLUENCE OF PHYSICAL ENVIRONMENT ON CUSTOMER LOYALTY TO RESTAURANTS SERVICES IN ENUGU METROPOLIS

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8274041>

Abstract: *The study investigated the influence of physical environment on customer loyalty to restaurants services in Enugu Metropolis. The specific objectives include; To determine the influence of functionality and customer loyalty to restaurants services in Enugu Metropolis. to ascertain the influence of aesthetics and customer loyalty to restaurants services in Enugu Metropolis and to examine the influence of convenience and customer loyalty to restaurants services in Enugu Metropolis. The study used survey research design. The sample size of the study was 384. Structured questionnaire was used for data collection. The reliability coefficient of questionnaire was 0.70 and this was measured using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient which showed consistency of the instrument. Regression tool was used in testing the hypotheses. After data analysis, findings revealed that functionality had a significant positive influence on customers' loyalty of restaurants services in Enugu Metropolis, aesthetics had a significant positive influence on customers' loyalty of restaurants services in Enugu Metropolis and convenience had a significant positive influence on customers' loyalty of restaurants services in Enugu Metropolis. The study concluded that functionality, aesthetics and convenience make customers to be loyal to restaurants services in Enugu metropolis. Based on the findings and conclusion reached, the following were made: Managers of restaurants firms should consider functionality, aesthetics and convenience as a powerful strategy tool for achieving customers' loyalty.*

Keywords: Physical Environment, Customer Loyalty, Restaurants Services

Introduction

A growing number of people are getting interested in the utilization of leisure time. This has increased the sports service industry market size, and its business characteristics are changing to be consumer oriented. Restaurants are one of the places to dine out in order to accommodate people's social and business activities (Wijaya, Widjaya & Hariyanto, 2016). In Nigeria, the culture of dining out has boosted the development of restaurant industry (Salleh, Hashima & Murphy, 2015). Evidence showed that, in general, the food and beverage establishments in Nigeria have witnessed an annual growth rate of 5.1% since 2010, amounting to 167,490 establishments (Department of Statistics Nigeria, 2016). Seemingly, there is growing number of

Nigerians' restaurants as the demand increases (Moorthy, Chee, Yi, Ying, Woen, & Wei, 2017). Looking at the growing patterns, fierce competition waits. Hence, ensuring its survival in the competitive market becomes crucial.

The physical environment was first introduced by Kotler in 1973, also known as the retail atmosphere. (Bitner, 2012) states that the physical environment is a set of services consisting of three components: environmental conditions, space and decor, and directional signs. According to (Ryu & Jang, 2017) a good physical environment can generate positive emotions, consumer intention, satisfaction, and consumer loyalty to a restaurant. of course, the quality of food is fundamental, but good working conditions and service will further influence the consumer's decision to make a purchase (Wall & Berry, 2017).

Shoemaker and Lewis (2019) suggest that keeping existing customers is one of the strategies in marketing. Restaurant operators should give serious attention to switch their marketing strategy from attracting new customers and keep existing once. Since the restaurants offer almost similar product and services, retaining loyal customers is the key survival in the competitive market. Ma, Qu and Eliwa (2014) identified three main reasons a restaurant might increase sales through loyal customer. First, loyal customers tend to be less price-sensitive, thus, slight change in pricing might not affect this group of customers. This is especially important for hotel restaurant where the restaurant is targeting group from business and corporate. Second, loyal customers visit more frequently and open for new menu and service offerings. Third, they are likely to spread positive word-of-mouth marketing, in which in return bringing new customers to the restaurant. Additionally, the effort of retaining loyal customers offer cost advantage as compared to attracting new customers (Wills, 2019).

Customer's demands had influenced the restaurant industry to fierce competitions (Majid, Alias, Samsudin & Chik, 2016). As a result of competitive market, it is important to understand the factors in keeping the customers loyal (Soriano, 2002) and provide economic advantage (Polyorat & Sophonsiri, 2010). By understanding the factors that associate with customers loyalty, customer's expectation might be satisfied, in return, generate plentiful revenue for the restaurant (Haghighi, Dorosti, Rahnama & Hoseinpour, 2012). Seemingly, the significance of these factors varied according to the type of restaurants. Among various factors, indeed, delivering good service is required in the business operation and regarded as an important factor in keeping the loyal customers. Quality of food is also one of the determinants that influence the customer loyalty especially in restaurant context. Adding to that, restaurant image is seen as an important attribute for hotel restaurants (Ismail, Zahari, Shariff & Suhaimi, 2016). Moreover, the restaurant carries the image of the hotel as it involved with the hotel operation. Therefore, service quality, food quality and image are employed in this study as the factors affecting customer loyalty in hotel restaurant.

Statement of the Problem

Customer loyalty is crucial to the success of many restaurants. As there are many restaurants that provide similar products and services, customers loyalty is the key to remain successful in business. Research found that it is a cost effective and valuable return for an organization as the loyal customers are willing to spend more. Therefore, it is imperative for every restaurant to retain loyal customers due to some positive outcome.

Previous studies in other establishment such as hotels and churches reveal that physical environment element in form of parking spaces, ambient temperature, music, architecture and design of the building influence customer patronage. However, there has been little focus on the influence of physical environment on customers' loyalty

in restaurants in Enugu metropolis. The need for this study become more intensified as restaurant managers spend huge amount of money on physical environment especially in the area of functionality, aesthetics and convenience with little or no knowledge of how this influence loyalty of their customers. As a result of this gap in knowledge this study tried to examine the influence of physical environment on customer loyalty to restaurants services in Enugu metropolis.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study is to investigate influence of physical environment on customer loyalty to restaurants services in Enugu Metropolis. Specifically, the objectives sought include:

- i. To determine the influence of functionality and customer loyalty to restaurants services in Enugu Metropolis.
- ii. To ascertain the influence of aesthetics and customer loyalty to restaurants services in Enugu Metropolis.
- iii. To examine the influence of convenience and customer loyalty to restaurants services in Enugu Metropolis.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Physical Environment

Physical environment is one of control variable under the study. Physical environmental space image as a critical factor which transforms the space into cultural space, attracts consumer satisfaction and loyalty, and further brings financial results to firms. And we supplemented the concepts of physical environment by Ko *et al.* (2009) with surrounding elements (proper temperature, proper indoor space, proper lighting, pleasant air, proper circulation area for users), functionality (proper door opening, the location of swing capturing cameras, screen clarity), aesthetics (colors of facilities, interior design features, aesthetic design, beautiful design, exclusive design), and convenience (convenient rest area and parking area). Kotler (1973) first defined atmosphere as 'efforts to design a purchase environment that could generate certain emotional. There are several elements or indicators that can shape a physical environment and support the consumer's attractiveness, exterior facilities, interior design, layout and location (Lupiyoadi, 2013).

Customer Loyalty

Attaining customer loyalty should be an essential component of an organization's long-term aim (Jin, Line & Goh, 2013; Srivastava & Rai, 2013). Importantly, loyal customers have higher commitment and stronger emotional bonds with the particular company (Gounaris & Stathakopoulos, 2004). Yoo and Bai (2013) affirm that loyal customers tend to become less susceptible with competitor's marketing strategies. Concept of customer loyalty is divided into two, namely behavioral and attitudinal. According to Alan and Kunal (1994), behavioral concept measures repeat patronage frequency and attitudinal concept refers to psychological commitment with the brand or business. In hospitality industry, the latter concept has been employed to measure customer loyalty (Han & Ryu, 2019; Schall, 2013; Mattila, 2001). A customer who has intention to repurchase and recommend to others has higher chance to remain with the restaurant (Kandampully & Suhartanto, 2000). Thus, in this study, attitudinal approach is used to assess customer loyalty of hotel restaurant.

Conceptual Framework

Conceptual framework is a structure designed by the researcher based on ideas from related theories models and findings from related empirical. The conceptual framework is presented in figure 2.1 below

Physical Environment

Customer Loyalty

Figure 2.1: Model of the influence of physical environment on customers’ loyalty to Restaurants Services in Enugu Metropolis.

Source: Adapted from Mehrabian-Russel. Stimulus – Response Model (1980).

The conceptual framework in figure 2.1 shows that a restaurant’s physical environment in terms of functionality, aesthetics and convenience is likely to influence the loyalty of its customers. Physical environment refers to the style and appearance of the physical surroundings and other experiential elements encountered by customers at service delivery sites (Ejionueme and Nebo, 2021). Customers intuitively respond to the signals that the external and internal environment project. Research has shown that appropriate physical environment is likely attracting target audience to a service offer. Major elements of the physical environment that attract customers to service organisation include: functionality, aesthetics and convenience.

Functionality and Customer Loyalty

Functionality Spatial layout refers to the ways in which machinery, equipment and furnishings are arranged, the size and shape of those items, and the spatial relations amongst them, and functionality refers to the ability of those items aforementioned to facilitate performance and also accomplishment of purpose which it’s meant for. Previous empirical research in psychology and organizational behavior of spatial layout and functionality dimensions always from the employees point of view (Sundstrum and Sundstrom, 2016). With the exception of some research on service organization layout, congestion, safety, comfort, confidence, and the use of orientation aids (Levine, Marchon, and Hanley 2014). Sense of belonging may also influence the spatial layout of customers within the environment and identification with a service provider. Though, not much has been done about the effects of spatial layout and functionality on customers in service organizational settings.

Aesthetics and Customer Loyalty

A growing body of literature is exploring the role of design, aesthetics and atmosphere in the hotel context. This is in response to the hotel sector innovating in the use of “form and function” to create products with segment specific appeal, perhaps best exemplified in the growth of boutique style hotels with “room-by-room distinctiveness” and “architectural spaces” where a “disproportionality large chunk of the design budget is allocated to the lobby and public areas” (McNeill, 2018). Design and art helps to strategically position the hotel making it part of the organization’s marketing activity (West and Purvis, 2012), leading to improved occupancy rates and increased average daily room rates (Countryman and Jang, 2016).

Convenience and Customer Loyalty

Convenience (CNV) Webster’s Dictionary defines convenience as “anything that adds to one’s comfort or saves work; useful, handy or helpful device, article, service, etc.” In the marketing context, is referred to convenience goods as those that the consumer purchases frequently and immediately at easily accessible stores Copeland (Copeland, 2013). It may also be defined as consumer perceptions regarding the relative time and effort expended in either purchasing or using a service (Berry, Seiders, and Grewal, 2002). Convenience has been one of the principal motivations underlying customer inclinations to adopt online purchasing (Easterbrook, 2015). In the current study, the author defines convenience in the context of Internet banking as an automated accessible online service 24 hours a day and seven days, that increases comfort for users while reducing the expenditure of time and effort on the part of using such an advanced technology.

Theoretical Framework

Mehradian-Russel Stimulus-Response Model

This theory holds that “feelings determine how people will respond to environment. It states that the conscious and unconscious perception and interpretation of the environment influences how people feel. People’s feelings in turn determine their reponses to that environment.

Figure 2.1 below is a diagrammatic representation of Mehrabian-Russl Stimulus-Response Model.

Figure 2.2: Mehrabian-Russel Stimulus-Response Model

The above model shows that environmental stimuli such as exterior facilities, general interior, ambient conditions, employees’ uniforms and behavior of a typical service personal and physical conditions of the service organization all can affect customer’s feelings or mood. Consumer mood state or feelings are expressed in various forms such as happiness, pleasure, confidence, joy, excitement, anger, frustration, anxiety, fear, depression, shame, guilt etc. consumer feelings will determine responses behaviour to the environment which may be approach or avoidance. Approach behaviour means that the customer feels good about the environment and this will result in business patronage while avoidance means that the customer dislikes the environment and may likely depart without buying anything. The implication of this theory to hospitality and tourism marketing is that managers of these firms should ensure that the physical environment elements such as interior decorations, exterior facilities, and employees corporate identity are designed to trigger favourable consumer feelings or mood states. Good feelings are likely to produce favourable purchase response (approach) (Ejionueme and Nebo, 2021).

Empirical Review

Eka., Muslim and Patar (2020) examined influence of lifestyle, physical environment, and menu variety on customer loyalty through customer satisfaction in Nigeria. The present study discusses the direct and indirect effects of lifestyle, physical environment, and menu variety on customer satisfaction through customer satisfaction. The results of the current study found that lifestyle is positively and significantly related to customer satisfaction, physical environment positively and significantly related to customer satisfaction, and menu variety are not related to customer satisfaction.

Türker, Gökkaya and Acar (2019) confirmed measuring the effect of restaurant servicescapes on customer loyalty in Nigeria. This paper aims to examine the perceptions of customers towards restaurant servicescapes and to find out the influential role of restaurant servicescapes in customer loyalty. Results indicate that both direct/indirect external servicescape influences and physical environment: external presentation had the highest scores that positively affect the loyalty of customers.

Sri and Eriana (2018) conducted a study on increasing customer loyalty of ethnic restaurant through experiential marketing and service quality in Indonesia. The purpose of this study was to examine the effect of experiential marketing, service quality on satisfaction and loyalty of ethnic restaurant consumers. The study found that experiential marketing and service quality have an effect on the satisfaction and loyalty of ethnic restaurant consumer

Anh and Thi (2016) investigated an analysis of factors impact on customer satisfaction in vietnam restaurants: case of fast food restaurants in UK. The primary purpose of this study was to explore the factors that investigate the customers' evaluation and perception about determinants influencing on customer satisfaction at Vietnamese fast-food restaurants. The study adopted survey research design. The findings from the study revealed that the current situation of each factor in Vietnam fast-food industry and how extremely influencing each factor is. Furthermore, these findings also provide useful strategies and understandable knowledge to improve and develop in Vietnamese fast-food restaurants as well as the satisfaction level from customers.

Ju (2016) conducted a study on effect of customer awareness of restaurants' green practices on customer dining experiences in USA. This study presents an integrated model to indicate how perceived service quality and perceived values are related to customer satisfaction, with customer awareness of restaurants' green practices as a moderator in perceived value-customer satisfaction linkage at green restaurants. The study results support the model, indicating that perceived service quality (both food quality and physical environmental quality), and perceived value are associated with customer satisfaction.

Ahmad and Norzalita (2012) examined the effect of physical environment's innovativeness on the relationship between hosting quality and satisfaction in Hotel Services in Nigeria. The aim of this study was to examine the moderating effect of physical environment's innovativeness (PEI) on the relationship between hosting quality and satisfaction in the hotel services. Hierarchical moderated regression analysis performed found statistical supports for the positive influence of hotel hosting quality on guest satisfaction as well as positive moderating effect of PEI.

Amer and Raja (2020) studied satisfaction and revisit intentions at fast food restaurants in Nigeria. This study was to identify the positive association of food quality, restaurant service quality, physical environment quality, and customer satisfaction with revisit intention of customers at fast food restaurants. The results confirmed positive association of food quality, restaurant service quality, physical environment quality, and customer satisfaction with revisit intentions of customers at fast food restaurants..

Gusti and Tinggi (2020) conducted an importance of physical environment for guest satisfaction on restaurant, advances in economics in Indonesia. The purpose of this study was to determine the factors and variables that can satisfy customers in restaurants in Bali. The results of research on the role of the physical environment on customer satisfaction in restaurants in Bali as a whole is in good condition. The most determining factor of customer satisfaction is the atmosphere factor (F2) followed by the facility's aesthetic factor (F1).

Matthew (2019) opined an article environmental aesthetics in the age of climate change auer school of public and international affairs in Nigeria. From this perspective, condemnation of peoples' enjoyment of climate-altered nature is beside the point, since moral concerns have no bearing on the intrinsic, aesthetic qualities of the observed entity. This paper argues that the autonomist perspective is challenged in a world of increasingly pervasive and negative encounters with climate-altered nature.

Demah, David and Nicholson (2019) examined the role of aesthetics and design in hotelscape. Should aesthetics and design be viewed as strategic marketing tools? We argue in this paper there are currently limited frameworks and empirical evidence to help should this be the ambition of marketers? We propose a hotelscape as a holistic evolution of the servicescape concept, which is developed to reflect the role that aesthetics and design can play in influencing consumer behaviour within moments of consumption.

Laith (2017) investigated framework for measuring the convenience of advanced technology on user perceptions of internet banking systems in Saudi Arabia. The main purpose of this current study was to examine the main keys to measure the merit perception of using Internet banking technology. The findings of the study indicate that all mentioned factors in the proposed model (CNV, SE, QI, AW, PEU, PU) have significant impact within prompting the use of Internet banking systems.

Gaps in Empirical Review

Much current literature has reviewed link to physical environment and customer loyalty. View of Eka., Muslim and Patar (2020) examined influence of lifestyle, physical environment, and menu variety on customer loyalty through customer satisfaction in Nigeria. The results of the current study found that lifestyle is positively and significantly related to customer satisfaction, physical environment positively and significantly related to customer satisfaction, and menu variety are not related to customer satisfaction. But this present study deemed it necessary to fill this gap of variables under the study, which introduced functionality, aesthetics and convenience as decomposition of physical environment of restaurants in Enugu State.

METHODOLOGY

For the purposes of this study, the researcher employed a survey research design. A survey design was concerned with determining the frequency with which something occurs or the relationship between variables (Bryman & Bell, 2003). Primary data is information gathered directly from respondents (Kombo & Tromp, 2006) and for this study; the researcher used primary data collected from questionnaire issued to respondents. The target population is comprised of customers' of the two selected restaurants services in Enugu metropolis which are Emily and Dolphin. This means that the customers' were unknown.

Sample size determination is the act of choosing from the population the number of respondents to reach for data collection. Since the population of the study is infinite, the researcher applied Topman's formular in determining the sample size. Topman's formular is given below:

unknown population using the mathematical function below:-

Therefore,

$$N = \frac{Z^2PQ}{e^2}$$

Where,

N = Sample size

Z = Standard normal probability distribution At 95% confidence level, Z value is 1.96

P = Probability of success of a standard (Normal distribution is 0.5%)

Q = Probability of failure of a standard (Normal distribution is 0.05%)

e = 5% limit of tolerable error.

Substituting the above values in the formula, we have

$$N = \frac{1.96^2 (0.5) (0.5)}{0.05^2}$$

$$N = \frac{3.8416 (0.5) (0.5)}{0.0025}$$

$$N = \frac{0.9604}{0.0025}$$

N = 384 Sample Size

The study adopted convenience sampling for selecting the respondents since sampling frame was not available. Structured questionnaire was adopted to collect data from the respondents within the Enugu Metropolis. The questionnaire was made up of 5 points Likert scale strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree (SA-SD). For each variable, there were (items/elements) which were deployed keeping in view the questionnaire filling culture and understanding of the population. The study employed inferential and descriptive statistics, inferential statistical tool used for the study was regression analysis while descriptive cover tables, percentage and frequencies.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSES

From table 4.1 above, it shows that 300 copies of the questionnaire were duly completed and returned representing 78.12 percent, while 84 copies of the questionnaire were not duly completed and returned from the respondents representing 21.88 percent. Therefore, the total of 300 copies questionnaire was used for the analysis

Test of Hypotheses

Test of Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Functionality had no significant positive influence on customer loyalty to restaurants services.

H_{a1}: Functionality has significant positive influence on customer loyalty to restaurants services.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.663a	.440	.431	.37617

Source: Author's Compilation, 2023

Predictors: (Constant), functionality table above revealed that there is a strong significant positive influence at R= .663 between functionality and customer loyalty to restaurants services. An examination of the table shows that R square = .440 which implies that functionality accounts for 44% of variations having a significant influence on customer loyalty.

ANOVA a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sign
1 Regression	20.123	3	6.708	47.403	.000b
Residual	25.612	27	.142		
Total	45.735	30			

Source: Author's Compilation, 2023

a. Dependent Variable: customers' loyalty b. Predictors: (Constant), functionality Table shows that the F-value is the Mean Square Regression (6.708) divided by the Mean Square Residual (0.142), yielding $F=47.403$. From the results, the model in this table is statistically significant ($Sig = .000$). Therefore, functionality had a significant positive influence on customers' loyalty at $F(3,184) = 47.403$.

Test of Hypothesis 2

Test of Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Aesthetics do not have significant positive influence on customer loyalty to restaurants services.

H_{a2}: Aesthetics has significant positive influence on customer loyalty to restaurants services.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.250a	.065	.047	.45468

Source: Author's Compilation, 2023

Predictors: (Constant), aesthetics. Table above revealed that there is a significant positive influence at $R = .250$ between aesthetics and customers' loyalty. An examination of the table shows that the R square = .063 which implies that aesthetics accounts for only 6.3% of variations having a significant positive influence on customers' loyalty.

ANOVA a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sign
1 Regression	2.503	3	.834	4.035	.008b
Residual	37.417	27	.207		
Total	39.921	30			

Source: Author's Compilation, 2023

a. Dependent Variable: customers' loyalty b. Predictors: (Constant), aesthetics with staff Table shows that the F-value is the Mean Square Regression (0.834) divided by the Mean Square Residual (0.207), yielding $F=4.035$. The model in this table shows that aesthetics statistically and significantly at ($Sig = .008$) and had a significant positive influence on customers' loyalty at $F(3,184) = 4.035$. The statistical results is given as; (aesthetics $\beta = .019$; $t = .171$; $p > 0.05$). The statistical result implies that aesthetics has statistically significant positive influence on customers' loyalty.

Test of Hypothesis 3

Test of Hypothesis Three

H₀₃: Convenience does not have significant positive influence on customer loyalty to restaurants services.

H_{a3}: Convenience has significant positive influence and customer loyalty to restaurants services.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.740a	.548	.541		.33794

Source: Author's Compilation, 2023

Predictors: (Constant), Customer loyalty. Table above revealed that there is a significant positive influence at $R = .740$ between convenience and customers' loyalty. An examination of the table shows that the R square = .548 which implies that convenience for 54.8% of variations having a significant positive influence on customers' loyalty.

ANOVA a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sign
1 Regression	25.064	3	.8355	73.155	.008b
Residual	20.671	27	.114		
Total	45.75	30			

Source: Author's Compilation, 2023

a. Dependent Variable: customers' loyalty b. Predictors: (Constant), convenience Table shows that the F-value is the Mean Square Regression (8.355) divided by the Mean Square Residual (0.114), yielding $F = 73.155$. The model reveals that convenience statistically and significantly at (Sig = .000) therefore it had a significant predictor at $F(3,184) = 73.155$. The statistical results is given as; (Convenience; $\beta = .146$; $t = 3.118$; $p < 0.05$). The statistical result implies that convenience had a statistically significant positive influence on customers' loyalty.

Discussion of Findings

Hypothesis One: Functionality had no significant positive influence on customer loyalty to restaurants services.

F-value is the Mean Square Regression (6.708) divided by the Mean Square Residual (0.142), yielding $F = 47.403$. From the results, the model in this table is statistically significant (Sig = .000). Therefore, functionality had a significant positive influence on customers' loyalty at $F(3,184) = 47.403$. According to Amer and Raja (2020) studied satisfaction and revisit intentions at fast food restaurants in Nigeria. Amongst other, Gusti and Tinggi (2020) conducted an importance of physical environment for guest satisfaction on restaurant, advances in economics in Indonesia. The results of research on the role of the physical environment on customer satisfaction in restaurants in Bali as a whole is in good condition.

Hypothesis Two: Aesthetics do not have significant positive influence on customer loyalty to restaurants services.

The model in this table shows that aesthetics statistically and significantly at (Sig =.008) and had a significant positive influence on customers' loyalty at $F(3,184) = 4.035$. The statistical results is given as; (aesthetics $\beta = .019$; $t = .171$; $p > 0.05$). The statistical result implies that aesthetics has statistically significant positive influence on customers' loyalty. Demah, David and Nicholson (2019) examined the role of aesthetics and design in hotelscape. The study is based on interviews with cosmopolitan type customers. An interpretive phenomenological approach is deployed to explore the lived experiences of art and design in a hotelscape. Even in view of Matthew (2019) opined an article environmental aesthetics in the age of climate change a school of public and international affairs in Nigeria. Revealed that the autonomist perspective is challenged in a world of increasingly pervasive and negative encounters with climate-altered nature.

Hypothesis Three: Convenience does not have significant positive influence on customer loyalty to restaurants services. The model reveals that convenience statistically and significantly at (Sig =.000) therefore it had a significant predictor at $F(3,184) = 73.155$. The statistical results is given as; (Convenience; $\beta = .146$; $t = 3.118$; $p < 0.05$). The statistical result implies that convenience had a statistically significant positive influence on customers' loyalty.

Laith (2017) investigated framework for measuring the convenience of advanced technology on user perceptions of internet banking systems in Saudi Arabia. The findings of the study indicate that all mentioned factors in the proposed model (CNV, SE, QI, AW, PEU, PU) have significant impact within prompting the use of Internet banking systems.

Summary of Findings

- i. Functionality had a significant positive influence on customers' loyalty of restaurants services in Enugu Metropolis.
- ii. Aesthetics had a significant positive influence on customers' loyalty of restaurants services in Enugu Metropolis.
- iii. Convenience had a significant positive influence on customers' loyalty of restaurants services in Enugu Metropolis.

Conclusion

Based on findings, we conclude that functionality, aesthetics and convenience of restaurants are primary factors that bring customer loyalty to restaurants services in Enugu metropolis.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the study recommends that: Managers of restaurants firms should consider functionality, aesthetics and convenience as a powerful strategy for achieving customers' loyalty.

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